

SPECIFIC QUALITIES OF THE INFORMATION EXCHANGE PROCESS

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Annotation: this article is written about the specifics of information and its exchange in international terms.

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The possibility of using the internet is today considered a requirement of the principle of cultural law, just like the possibility of using libraries in the last century, and it is for this reason that at a meeting of the UN General Assembly it was stated that the use of the internet is a necessary instrument for a person to express his opinion, For the population, it is meant not only to re-view the exchange of opinions and information of representatives of different nationalities in 12 environments over the internet. Further study of these processes encourages the population to reflect on how well the general productive use of their cultural resources is. In doing so, of course, we must use the internet to ensure how important the information is in this regard. In this we can have obstacles from different technical and linguistic points of view but even with regard to this process, the experts say that production is being improved today in terms of language possibilities to give information in different languages, and this in turn allows integration to maintain cultural identity in processes. Like any communication, the process of information exchange in the environment can be both direct and indirect. In the world of the Internet, the state of information exchange is affected by the indirect communication process, the possibilities of which are as wide as the possibilities of the internet. The past stage of the development of the world media on the internet makes it possible to define internet journalism as a separate type of information activity and distinguish its specific features. As specific aspects of the internet as a media, the following can be requested. The fact that the network has a global scale, the speed in data transmission is not centralized in the work process, it is open to everyone, it is controlled by the user, it is economically convenient. It can be said that these aspects characterize the audience in it. Among the concepts related to the Internet, constantly we mean globality, speed, digitization, Interactive in the sense of content, too, it can be said that these concepts reflect its characteristics. The information provided in the Internet environment does not meet their full requirements in the absence of these indicators. While globality is explained by

the fact that it has a global scale of information and information recipients, interactivity, in turn, implies the presence of a bilateral dialogue between the audience and the media. Globality, on the other hand, represents the possibility that none of the other media have access to many resources that are unparalleled behind a page, being considered an aspect that does not exist. The possibility of familiarization with the much earlier information of the publication of the Web page in digital form as an archiving resource is considered concepts. It was these features that caused the number of internet users to increase from year to year. Despite being world aspects of internet journalism it has absorbed organizational aspects from print media, which has received several features from traditional media types, and from radio-Fast Live broadcast to TV journalism, it has absorbed exhibitionism and illustrative opportunities. but despite the fact that the imbalance in the use of digital technologies causes inequality in information retrieval, which is manifested in the following cases when in the process of obtaining information, the population of the world has inequality in relation to access to inequality against the modern information environment and inequality within the family in relation to participation in the process of

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